

Annual Plan 2021 – 2022

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1 Message from the Director

I am delighted and excited to present our programme of work for the next year. The past year has seen the ODISSEI roadmap project launch into life, and it has been wonderful to witness the rapid growth and welcome so many new and enthusiastic colleagues. The plan set out in this document outlines how we plan to turn these bright beginnings into meaningful change in the way social science research is conducted. This plan of work was constructed from the bottom up by the numerous task leaders in ODISSEI. They developed programmes of work in collaboration with the ODISSEI Coordination Team. These plans were then discussed, amended and approved by the Management Board

There are many new initiatives and opportunities within ODISSEI, but there are a few that I am particularly looking forward to in the new year. Firstly, I am particularly proud to see ODISSEI develop into a FAIR implementation community through the work conducted by the ODISSEI portal team. This work not only aids the work of social scientists but also makes it easier to link social science data with other domains and ensure that social sciences can be integrated in life sciences, environmental sciences and the humanities.

Secondly, I have greatly enjoyed seeing ODISSEI work to make even more datasets available for researchers and the next year will see a new team of data scouts, managers and stewards that will intensify these efforts. Since its inception ODISSEI has focused on integrating existing data collections but it also needs to expand the amount and types of data available for researchers.

Finally, I am looking forward to the having the inspiring programme of events we have established become face-to-face meetings, when conditions allow for it. There are many new colleagues that we have only seen online, and it will be exciting to meet the vibrant and expanded ODISSEI community in person. Hopefully this will be possible for our annual community day in the fall, and I hope you will join us.

Beyond the work plan outlined here, the Management Board will continue to identify new funding opportunities and ways to further develop the infrastructure. We are working with colleagues from across the Social Sciences and Humanities on plans for the future roadmap and the investments of the Platform Digital Infrastructure (PDI) SSH call have sparked a diverse range of new opportunities to innovate and collaborate.

Pearl Dykstra
Scientific director, ODISSEI

2 Governance

ODISSEI now consists of **40 member organisations** who have all signed the participants agreement and committed their financial contribution to ODISSEI until 2024, the end of the Roadmap project.

The **Supervisory Board** consists of Pieter Hooimeijer (DSW, chair), Carlo Schuengel (DSW), Henk van der Kolk (DSW), Arthur van Soest (DEB), Ruben Dood (Statistics Netherlands), Peter van der Laan (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), and Sander Steijn (public research institutes).

The **Management Board** consists of nine members: Pearl Dykstra (EUR, Chair and Director), Tom Emery (EUR, Deputy Director), Dorret Boomsma (VU), Tanja van der Lippe (UU), Marcel Das (Centerdata), Annette Scherpenzeel (Statistics Netherlands), Annette Langedijk (SURF), Rob van Nieuwpoort (NLeSC), and Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU). The Management Board meets monthly to discuss and evaluate the program of work. In June 2021, the Supervisory Board will be asked to approve the appointment of Henk Wals (DANS) as a tenth member of the board to represent DANS's vital contribution to the development of ODISSEI.

The Coordination Team now consists of six individuals Pearl Dykstra (Director), Tom Emery (Deputy Director), Lucas van der Meer (Operational Manager), Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Suze Zijlstra (Community Manager), and Eva Heitbrink (Community Manager). In summer 2021, a new Data Manager will be hired to assist with FAIR implementation within ODISSEI.

An **International Advisory Board** has been established including Ron Dekker (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, CESSDA), Julia Lane (New York University), Melinda Mills (University of Oxford), Sally Wyatt (Maastricht University), and Amy O'Hara (Georgetown University). Due to travel restrictions the board has yet to meet in person, but a virtual meeting took place in May 2021.

3 Programme of Work

ODISSEI conducts activities in four work streams as defined in the ODISSEI Roadmap proposal: the Data Facility, the Observatory, the Laboratory, and the Hub. This section details those activities and the work that is planned for the period 2021-2022.

3.1 The Data Facility

3.1.1 Statistics Netherlands Microdata Access

ODISSEI stimulates the use of the rich microdata at Statistics Netherlands (CBS), particularly amongst early career researchers and first-time users. These pseudonymised microdata are available at the level of individuals, companies, and addresses. The data are made available to researchers in the secured Statistics Netherlands environment under strict conditions for statistical research¹, and can be combined with researchers' own datasets. However, the costs for obtaining access to the microdata can be prohibitive, especially for early-career researchers.

In early 2022, ODISSEI will launch its annual call to facilitate access to microdata from Statistics Netherlands free of charge for researchers at ODISSEI member organisations (so-called Microdata Access Grants, MAG). Around **six projects** will be granted in Summer 2021 with a total allocation of **€ 60,000**. The amounts awarded are small with an average amount of € 7,500 but the impact of access is large, and these projects would not be possible without them. In 2021, ODISSEI is trying to stimulate further use of CBS Microdata in combination with data from other sources. There are therefore two dedicated calls for microdata with the Longitudinal Internet Study for the Social Sciences (LISS) Panel and the *Nationaal Kiezersonderzoek* (NKO) from the 2021 election.

ODISSEI will continue the Microdata Access Discount (MAD) in collaboration with Statistics Netherlands. ODISSEI provides a discount of up to 50% to Statistics Netherlands microdata projects from ODISSEI member organisations. The topics are immensely diverse, covering crime, health sciences, demography, environmental issues and genetics to name a few. The total value of these discounts for the coming year is **€ 300,000**. A full list of projects that receive the discount is available on the ODISSEI website. Member organisations are prohibited from claiming more than double their annual contributions. In 2021, Statistics Netherlands is conducting an evaluation of Microdata Access within ODISSEI to identify more efficient ways (than the current MAD and MAG schemes) to stimulate and support usage of microdata for research purposes. The first stage of this is a survey of researchers at ODISSEI member organizations. The results of the evaluation will lead to a revised microdata access program for the year 2022-23.

Task Leader: Annette Scherpenzeel (ac.scherpenzeel@cbs.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Annette Scherpenzeel (ac.scherpenzeel@cbs.nl)

¹ <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/our-services/customised-services-microdata/microdata-conducting-your-own-research>

3.1.2 ODISSEI Use Cases

There are a number of projects that operate across the ODISSEI infrastructures which require additional coordination and support. These projects tend to be more logistically complex but also highly innovative and technically challenging. Such projects make high demands of the infrastructure and the interoperability of various components whilst simultaneously demonstrating the concrete, scientific added value of an integrated approach that ODISSEI makes possible.

Given the demands and complexity of such projects, a core support team was established within the coordination team consisting of Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Tom Emery (Deputy Director) and Lucas van der Meer (Operations Manager). This team meets regularly to discuss the intake of projects across ODISSEI, including the Social Data Analytics team (SoDA), in SoDa, LISS, eScience, ODISSEI Secure Super Computer (OSSC), and CBS to identify projects that require additional coordination and potentially additional resources.

There have been several previous projects such as support for the *KansenKaart* (<https://kansenkaart.nl/>) which utilized SoDa, CBS microdata and the computational environment of the OSSC to scale up the data processing. A further example is the development of the network data file at CBS which uses CBS microdata to construct a whole population network of the Netherlands using the OSSC, consisting of 17 million people and 1.4 billion links between them.

The aim is to assist projects that use multiple pieces of infrastructure and develop them into flagship projects which demonstrate the potential of ODISSEI. The resources of this task for 2021-22 are modest (€ 45,412) and include costs of coordination and auxiliary technical support.

Task Leader: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

Statistics Netherlands and SURF delivered an operational version of the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC) in September 2020. This facility is a global first enabling the analysis of highly sensitive administrative data that is linked to data from social surveys and other sources in a secure HPC environment. The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer provides the fastest computing capacity in the Netherlands via the national supercomputer and obeys the highest standards for data protection both legally and technically. Datasets include pseudonymised administrative microdata on persons, households, companies etc. from Statistics Netherlands as well as research data collected by ODISSEI

members. Analysis of these highly secured datasets is possible due to the system’s architecture: SURF acts as Trusted Third Party between the data provider and the researcher, and the analysis environment is strictly controlled and protected. In August 2020, the OSSC illustrated its security by passing a second penetration test performed by the digital security company Secura².

Table 1 – Projects currently using the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

Researcher	Affiliation
Trond Husby	Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving (PBL)
Ana Petrović	TU Delft (TUD) - Faculty Architecture and the Built Environment
Maciek Strak	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM)
Elenna Dugunji	Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica (CWI)
Jasper Selder	Amsterdam UMC
Bastian Ravesteijn	Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam (EUR) - Erasmus School of Economics

Operation of the OSSC will cost **€ 159,216** in 2021-2022 which is exclusively for SURF. A further **€ 478,788** is planned for the development of the OSSC environment for research, which is shared between SURF and CBS. This includes the costs of a penetration test and adaptations to ensure the OSSC can service all member organisations. The OSSC was formally launched in October 2020 and now has capacity to support 15 projects per year. Interest in the OSSC has been considerable and comes from a wide variety of member organisations, as well as from organisations that are not ODISSEI members. Six projects have already begun working on the OSSC with a further room for 9 projects throughout the year. Through 2021-22 these projects will be supported in their implementation and usage of OSSC with the Coordination Team monitoring progress.

Task Leader: Michel Scheerman (michel.scheerman@surf.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Annette Langedijk (annette.langedijk@surf.nl)

² www.secura.com/penetration-testing

3.1.4 ODISSEI Portal

The ODISSEI Portal promotes the reuse of existing datasets by making them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Reusing and linking existing datasets can result in lower research costs, better data quality and richer data. By combining and linking datasets, new research questions can be addressed. To facilitate FAIR use of data, the portal will provide a variable level, searchable catalogue of data within ODISSEI member organisations.

The Portal working group was established and consists of representatives from **DANS**, VU, SURF and the ODISSEI Coordination team. Under this working group, the preliminary design and development of the Portal has begun with bi-weekly meetings and consultation with initial key strategic data providers at Statistics Netherlands and Centerdata. The budget for this work in 2021-2022 is € 274,077 and primarily consists of engineers, developers and data stewards. The aim is to develop a first iteration of the Portal by June 2022 in which administrative data at Statistics Netherlands and panel data from LISS are searchable through the same portal. This will help researchers who are applying to use LISS or Statistics Netherlands microdata through ODISSEI grants and access discounts in navigating the pre-existing data collections and rapidly identifying possible linkages and synergies between the data sources. In 2022-2024, further data sources will be added to extend the coverage and functionality of the Portal.

Task Leader: [Jacco van Ossenbruggen \(j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl\)](mailto:j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: [Lucas van der Meer \(lucas@odissei-data.nl\)](mailto:lucas@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: [Jacco van Ossenbruggen \(j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl\)](mailto:j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl)

3.2 The Observatory

3.2.1 ODISSEI Data Collection Committee

The ODISSEI Data Collection Committee facilitates collaboration and aims to transition the long-standing data collections into a coherent and sustainable future in which they are well placed within a more diverse and dynamic data landscape. ODISSEI ensures Dutch participation in cross-national data collections works to identify critical gaps in the data landscape and allocate resources to sustain longitudinal data collections. The Data Collection Committee will support data collections transition to sustainable operational models, the integration of new data collection methodologies and linkages with secure, register data via the Data Facility. Four members have been appointed: Marike Knoef (Chair), Gerbert Kraaykamp, Ineke Stoop, and Bella Struminskaya. Tom Emery acts as the Coordination Team support for the committee.

In 2021-22 the committee will be overseeing the implementation and reporting of the European Social Survey, the Dutch Election Study, the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe, and the Generations and Gender Survey. This coordination has become increasingly important given the impact of the COVID pandemic on fieldwork operations. ODISSEI finances Dutch participation in ERIC surveys and surveys of key strategic importance. In 2021-22, ODISSEI is financing data collection for the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (€ 550,000) and the coordination of the European Social Survey (€ 45,000). ODISSEI will also pay the Dutch contribution for the Luxembourg Income Study (€ 30,000).

As Chair of the Data Collection Committee, Marike Knoef also oversees data scouts who identify new sources of data for integration within ODISSEI (the ODISSEI Data Portal, linkage to CBS Microdata, use of secure data environments etc), especially data that has not been collected for research purposes and particularly in the fields of Law and Economics which are currently under-represented within the ODISSEI framework. The data scouts work with potential data providers and existing ODISSEI services to facilitate access to such data sets, ensure their adequate documentation and promote their usage. For 2021-22, this work is budgeted as € 84,464.

Task Leader: Marike Knoef (m.g.knoef@law.leidenuniv.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.2.2 Media Content Analysis Lab

The ODISSEI Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) will offer opportunities for systematic analysis of large corpora of digital media content. MCAL tackles the major challenge of digital text analysis whereby copyright and GDPR restrictions make it very hard to share media content data by providing a workbench for researchers where they can share data and analyses with strict rights management, without the need to read or export the data themselves. Currently, several Dutch initiatives exist that facilitate retrieval, storage, and analysis of media content (i.e. the infrastructure for content analysis [INCA] at the University of Amsterdam (Trilling et al., 2018), and the Amsterdam Content Analysis Toolkit [AMCaT] at VU Amsterdam (Van Atteveldt et al., 2014). Their use, however, requires considerable programming skills and is currently tailored to a limited set of applications.

³Through MCAL, the large amount of longitudinal media content data (i.e. online news data; social media data) currently available within ASCoR at University of Amsterdam and Communication Science VU will be made available to researchers at ODISSEI member organizations. It will also be possible to use specific tools on data stored elsewhere. First, an initial set of pre-existing tools will be identified - ranging from scrapers to collect content from specific sources to the extraction of meta information to scripts to conduct topic modelling, sentiment analysis, word embedding models, various forms of machine learning and deep learning (for a concise overview see Boumans & Trilling, 2018). Next, suitable existing textual corpora will be added to the database. Accessibility will be increased by composing a range of manuals. Moreover, the opportunity to apply the content analytical tools on one's own datasets will be added. The work will be conducted by a post-Doc appointed at UvA budgeted for **€ 61,538** through 2021-22.

Task Leader: Rens Vliegenthart (m.g.knoef@law.leidenuniv.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.2.3 Historical Sample of the Netherlands

To support links between historical and contemporary data on social processes, data from the Historical Sample of the Netherlands (HSN) will be linked with Statistics Netherlands Microdata (Social Statistical Database SSD). In practical terms, this involves the creation of a key for the persistent identifiers of individuals in the HSN and the persistent identifier for the same individual in the Social Statistical Database which is available in ODISSEI via CBS microdata services. Using this link, it is possible to trace the outcomes of the individuals in the HSN and their descendants forward to the current day. This will enable connections between the historical research conducted using the HSN and contemporary society and the outcomes studied by social scientists. This line of research will also enable stronger links with CLARIAH and the broader field of socio-economic history more generally.

Figure 1 - Lexis diagram showing the main sources of the HSN's life course data and the integration with the SSD dataset and the censuses of 1960 and 1971

The budget allocated for HSN in 2021-2022 is € 72,398 A Senior Scientist will oversee the proof-of-concept and provide scientific direction, setting priorities for the linkage of specific elements of the HSN cohort in order to achieve a production ready product. A Data coordinator will be responsible for the curation of the linked data and coordination with a team at Statistics Netherlands. A research assistant will help with data cleaning and linkage of the HSN cohorts and the linkage with SSD data. In addition, the proof-of-concept HSN-SSD will be supported by staff at Statistics Netherlands financed by the budget.

Task Leader: Richard Zijdemans (richard.zijdemans@iisg.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.2.4 National Twin Registry

⁴The work conducted by the National Twin Register (NTR) focuses on linking biomedical and cognitive data with the wider ODISSEI infrastructure through proof-of-concept projects within the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer and integrating and consolidating existing research on pedigrees across microdata projects at Statistics Netherlands. The work forms a key bridge to the work conducted in Consortium on Individual Development (CID)⁵ and BBMRI (Netherlands Biobank Research Facility)⁶ and consists of two tasks.

The first task is to broaden the scope of record linkage of cohort data and CBS data conducted as part of the OSSC pilot to include multiple external cohorts. The goal is to build on the procedures set up by the NTR teams and develop a standard operating procedure (SOP) for linking and analysing multiple external data sources with CBS data at once. This would allow for the pooling of cohorts and subsequent linkage to CBS microdata, greatly increasing the diversity of research questions that can be answered about specific sub-populations.

The second task defines a thorough network of family ties in the CBS data by including the classifications of genetic resemblance and creating a standardized method of defining family ties. Currently, the genetic and social pedigree structures are limited because information on parent-offspring relationships, that forms the basis for pedigree definitions, is often only available for two generations: children born after 1966, and their parents, and does not differentiate between biological and non-biological parents (see task 3.2.3). These data will be enriched with information from various sources to generate a comprehensive network of family ties that includes the genetic resemblance of all individuals in the Netherlands. Possibilities for differentiating between mono- and dizygotic twins based on CBS microdata or other external data sources (e.g. perined.nl, palgaopenbaredatabank.nl) will be developed. The budget for this work in 2021-22 will be **€ 70,909**.

Task Leader: Dorret Boomsma (di.boomsma@vu.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Dorret Boomsma (di.boomsma@vu.nl)

⁴ <https://unsplash.com/@nci>

⁵ <https://individualdevelopment.nl/>

⁶ <https://www.bbmri.nl/>

3.3 The Laboratory

3.3.1 Distributed Analytics

Data about people are sensitive owing to privacy concerns and issues relating to data protection.

This task explores the use of novel privacy-preserving technologies in order to understand the influence of special need students in relation to the health and well-being of their teachers and other students. Achieving this objective requires legitimate access to data that are collected and maintained by different organisations, with different policies concerning their potential

reuse. The overall objective of this work is to explore the feasibility of applying the privacy-preserving distributed analytics technologies (e.g., Personal Health Train technology). The work is made up of 3 sub-tasks:

Privacy-preserving technology: Develop methods that expose metadata in such a way that it does not reveal specific and privacy-sensitive attributes of a particular population, but rather exposes a constrained vocabulary that could be used to query the target data.⁷

Legal-ethical framework: Identify possible legal routes for the proposed research to occur, with a particular emphasis on the role that privacy-preserving technologies can play in fostering trust, transparency, and accountability.

Social science research: A scalable and reproducible statistical pipeline on social-emotional metrics from questionnaires. The pipeline will consider alternative proxies for current metrics (by now stress is measured by absenteeism). Before being prototyped on real queries, the pipeline will be developed using synthetic data testing the scalability and reproducibility parts.

The project team will collaborate with Netherlands Initiative for Education Research (NRO), who maintains close connections to the schools who will make available the education-related data, and with a researcher of the Inspectorate of Education, who seeks to perform the analysis, and finally with Statistics Netherlands (CBS), who has relevant microdata and has established a research-grade secure computing environment to undertake privacy-preserving research. For the year 2021-22, the budget of this task is € 89,157 which is exclusively for project staff.

Task Leader: [Michel Dumontier \(michel.dumontier@maastrichtuniversity.nl\)](mailto:michel.dumontier@maastrichtuniversity.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: [Lucas van der Meer \(lucas@odissei-data.nl\)](mailto:lucas@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: [Jacco van Ossenbruggen \(j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl\)](mailto:j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl)

^{7 7} Photo credit: <https://unsplash.com/@taypaigey>

3.3.1 Automated Linkage

This task is focused on applying innovations in information science to enhance the work conducted within the portal. The ODISSEI Portal aims to make research datasets findable by providing an advanced search interface on the data records describing these data sets. We refer to these records as the metadata. The better the quality of these metadata records, the better the Portal's functionality. While the main responsibility for providing high-quality metadata lies with the data owners and data providers in the project, it is expected that (semi) automatic enrichment of metadata of ODISSEI datasets can also help to improve the metadata used in the Portal.

The goal of this task is to design and develop methods and techniques for (semi) automatic enrichment of metadata of ODISSEI datasets. Special focus is on improving metadata for sensitive datasets, to help researchers 1) find these datasets and 2) help them assess their applicability to their research before requesting access to the actual data. An example of this is work completed in 2020-21 to express details on data access and licensing. Information about data constraints (such as whether the data can be used for academic or commercial purpose, if the data can be downloaded and allows for derivative works, how attribution must be given to original work) has been extracted from the license and policy agreements applied to the data. Such information is not intrinsically present in the metadata, and therefore it enriches it by providing: 1) options for searching and filtering to users (a researcher, for example, can filter through depending on the requirement for Academic Use of the dataset), 2) details about the use of the data to improve applicability to their research.

For the year 2021-22, the budget of this task is **€ 72,398** which is exclusively for project staff.

Task Leader: [Jacco van Ossenbruggen \(j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl\)](mailto:j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: [Lucas van der Meer \(lucas@odissei-data.nl\)](mailto:lucas@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: [Jacco van Ossenbruggen \(j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl\)](mailto:j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl)

3.3.3 The LISS Panel

The LISS panel, managed by Centerdata, consists of some 7,000 individuals from approximately 4,500 households. The panel is a representative sample of the adult population in the Netherlands. In June 2021, ODISSEI launched the fourth round of the **LISS Grant**. The calls are exceptionally popular. Successful projects are showcased on the ODISSEI website⁸ and generate considerable press attention. The call closes on 23 September.

All proposals that meet the eligibility criteria are assessed by the Centerdata team for feasibility. They are then submitted for peer-review. Reviewers scores will be returned by the end of November and the decision announced by mid-December. The projects will commence from February 2022. These calls cost € **95,000** for 2021-22.

In addition to the LISS Grants, ODISSEI will provide a **€ 425,000 subsidy to the LISS panel**. This budget will be used for the maintenance of the LISS panel in 2021-2022 and includes € 175,000 for refreshment of the panel to ensure continued representativity. The remaining fixed annual costs include personnel costs for panel management, subscription of broadband connection for panel members with initially no internet access, maintenance of hardware on loan to panel members, server and software license costs, and incentive costs for updating background variables and activation of 'sleeping' panel members (as to avoid attrition). Costs for the core study mainly consist of incentives for panel members, but also personnel costs for programming, testing, data cleaning and data dissemination.

As a recognition to ODISSEI of the provided subsidy, Centerdata provided a 20% discount for using the LISS panel to projects from ODISSEI member organisations. Over the course of 2021-2022, the team at Centerdata and the ODISSEI Coordination team will evaluate the manner in which the grants are administered to ensure optimal use of the panel for the research community. This may result in changes to the grant structure for the year 2022-23.

Task Leader: Marcel Das (marcel.das@centerdata.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Marcel Das (marcel.das@centerdata.nl)

⁸ <https://odissei-data.nl/en/2020/04/odissei-funds-corona-research-in-the-liss-panel/>

3.3.4 Mass online experiments

A mass online experiment is when 100 people or more are invited to participate in an online game. In each game, players interact with others to complete a task or aim. Social scientists can run experiments through such games by altering its rules or structures and seeing how this affects players behaviour. These techniques have been used very successfully to understand social behaviour such as how fake news spreads, how people form their voting intentions and how people evaluate the quality of information they find online. Yet these experiments are difficult and expensive to run, especially in the Netherlands where they are not well established. Players need to be recruited and incentivized, the experiments have to be designed and constructed and the game has to be hosted and supervised. A lot of this requires very specific skills and tools that are in short supply in the social sciences and humanities. This leads to high fixed costs as a barrier to ground-breaking research in psychology, sociology and economics. This task aims at designing a platform that addresses these issues and will significantly reduce or even eliminate the fixed costs associated with such experiments for Dutch researchers.

Exploratory work on the development of a Mass Online Experiment Platform includes two sociological studies. The first investigates how the spread of misinformation is impacted by the presence of echo chambers in a social network. An experimental infrastructure was built that could accommodate sessions in which true and false information was interactively and simultaneously shared among 192 liberal and conservative subjects distributed across two networks, one with echo chambers and one without. The second will further refine the technical specifications and requirements of the infrastructure and will be completed in 2021-2022. It requires a budget of € 57,614, primarily to cover the cost of a developer.

Fig. 1. Experimental design. (A) Subjects were randomly assigned to either an ideologically integrated (left) or segregated network (right) in which red (blue) nodes represent self-identified conservative (liberal) participants. (B) Each diffusion process (16 networks \times 32 messages = 512 in total) was initiated by a random seed node, who received an ideologically aligned message, and had it automatically shared with their 6 neighbors. We show the observed propagation history of a false conservative-leaning message in an integrated (left) and segregated network (right). Node size decreases with the shortest distance (1 to 8) to the seed node. The message read “*Children raised by homosexual parents experience more mental health issues than children raised by heterosexual parents.*”

Task Leader: Rense Corten (R.Corten@uu.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Rob van Nieuwpoort (R.vanNieuwpoort@esciencecenter.nl)

3.4 The Hub

3.4.1 Community Management

ODISSEI has forty member organisations and is open for others to join. There are a lot of potential users whose research would benefit from the infrastructure ODISSEI offers. Some have heard of the possibilities, but do not know ODISSEI can support them in using the infrastructure. Others already use ODISSEI but are not aware of all the infrastructure has to offer. It is important that they continue to stay involved or use the infrastructure more widely. The goal of Community Management is, first, to ensure that all potential users in relevant disciplines have high-quality knowledge of ODISSEI available so they can understand its use and importance (inform). Those (potential) users should be encouraged to take the next step in engagement with ODISSEI (activate). Those who are already involved should be stimulated to stay involved to broaden and deepen their involvement (retain). For that purpose, Community Management will deploy a wide range of activities to inform, involve and engage the community.

Inform the ODISSEI community, through regular updates and accessible information:

- News items on the website.
- Newsletter.
- Posts on Twitter and LinkedIn.
- Knowledge clips on ODISSEI facilities.
- Podcast series on ODISSEI infrastructure

Involve the ODISSEI Community, so it stays enthusiastic and active:

- Annual community conference.
- Task Insights meetings.
- Lunch lecture series around ODISSEI research projects.

Engage potential users, not yet familiar with ODISSEI:

- Grant information workshops.
- Events in collaboration with members.
- Roadshows..

The community management costs for 2021-22 are € **354,933** and include the costs of the ODISSEI coordination team.

Task Leader: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Annette Langedijk (annette.langedijk@surf.nl)

3.4.2 Educational Programme

ODISSEI offers researchers resources to work with large scale data collections and new forms of data and data analysis. However, not all researchers have the necessary expertise to work with the resources and facilities ODISSEI offers. In addition, the field of computational social sciences is fast-changing and developing. Therefore, ODISSEI wants to match researchers with tools to work with data in new ways and point researchers to courses that can help them gain the necessary expertise to work with these tools. ODISSEI has developed an educational programme for researchers in which they can advance their knowledge of computational social science. The team ensures the educational programme is an asset of ODISSEI that is useful and practical to researchers. The educational programme focuses on researchers who wish to start working with computational methods and inventory the needs of those who already are.

The programme is geared towards using specific ODISSEI facilities, with workshops tailored to potential and current users of ODISSEI facilities, such as the Microdata Access Grant and Discount, the LISS panel Grant and the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer. These workshops aim to inform researchers of the ins and outs of ODISSEI facilities and lower the threshold for submitting a project proposal. The programme is developed in collaboration with, and executed by or together with, several ODISSEI partners: Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), CBS, Centerdata, Netherlands eScience Center (NLLeSC) and SURF.

The team also works with the graduate schools and ODSSEI member organizations to coordinate existing efforts and where feasible identify and help address gaps in the existing provision of training and education in the Dutch Computational Social Science community. For 2021-22, the educational team will deliver approximately 5 workshops aimed at using the ODISSEI infrastructure and focused on thematic areas of interest such as geospatial analysis or network analysis. The costs of operating the ODISSEI educational programme for 2021-22 are **€ 40,376** and include the costs of coordination and resources for hosting events.

Task Leader: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Rob van Nieuwpoort (R.vanNieuwpoort@esciencecenter.nl)

3.4.3 ODISSEI Social Data Analytics

The Social Data Analytics Team bridges the gap between applied social scientists and the data, computing, and analytical infrastructure provided by ODISSEI. They seek out short-term collaborative projects with social scientists across ODISSEI member organisations to uniquely leverage ODISSEI's infrastructure to answer novel substantive questions and to build expertise in computational social science. These projects will result not only in 'traditional' publications, but also in open-source reusable code that can be used for teaching purposes or as a starting point for other projects. The current work is focused on developing a procedure for identifying and prioritising social data analytics projects and defining the scope of the team. The team supports researchers using other components of the infrastructure such as the OSSC, Microdata or LISS.

The projects SoDa takes on come from ODISSEI grants, activities, and community events, as well as direct contact with researchers. As such, there is necessarily a large variation in the type research question, data, and solution required. The primary purpose, however, is to do projects that:

- Are truly *collaborative*, in the sense that both the SoDa team and the substantive researchers are equal partners in decisions regarding the setup of the study, data analysis, software design, and peer-reviewed publication(s);
- Bring *added value* to the field, either by answering interesting social-scientific research questions using (ODISSEI) data and/or computational methods that could not have been answered otherwise, or by enabling such answers through the development of research software and modelling – and ideally, both;
- Adhere to the *highest standards* of reproducibility, open science, and research integrity.

The SoDa team is growing rapidly and consists of Daniel Oberski (PI), Erik-Jan van Kesteren (Team Leader), Jonathan de Bruin, Gerbrich Ferdinands, Helen Lam and will soon be extended with the appointment of an additional team member. This team has the capacity to greatly increase the number of projects conducted during 2021-2022 and cost **€ 224,257**. The primary focus in the early months of this year will be the alignment with eScience grant applications and the identification of new projects to make use of the teams services.

Task Leader: Daniel Oberski (d.l.oberski@uu.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Rob van Nieuwpoort (R.vanNieuwpoort@esciencecenter.nl)

3.4.4 eScience Grants

In this task grants are provided for computational social science to support the use of the data infrastructure developed across ODISSEI. These grants provide hours from eScience Research Engineers (RSEs) employed at the eScience center to collaborate with social scientists to enhance their research, by exploiting digital technologies. The grants are available via an annual open call, which will be assessed by a panel with members from ODISSEI and the eScience center. The deadline for the period 2021-2022 is July 30 2021. An online information event for this call was held on 10 June. The call in 2021 is exclusively for small pathfinder grants (405 engineering hours with a value of € 25K). These pathfinders are pilot projects suitable for researchers just starting in the field, to explore the use of digital technologies for their research. Six projects will be granted in 2021-22 and in conjunction with coordination costs and alignment with SoDa, the budget is **€ 191,833**. In subsequent years, larger grants will be available for more ambitious projects.

This produces a staircase approach to computational support, where researchers can ask for more support in larger projects, if needed. This staircase can start with consultancy from the SoDa team, followed by an eScience pathfinder grant, and ultimately a larger eScience grant. Finally, this process also ensures that the researchers are well positioned to apply for a full project in the eScience center open calls. Vice versa, successful eScience projects may lead to new SoDa followup projects as well. The main differences with the calls that will be organized by the SoDa team are:

- The eScience grants can include but are not limited to analytics. Instead, with the eScience grants, researchers can get support for a broad range of digital methods, ranging from data management, linking of datasets, analytics, visualization, machine learning, high-performance computing, natural language processing, etc.
- eScience grants are significantly larger and aim to answer a research question from start to finish in a collaborative project.
- Because of the larger scale of the eScience grants, a proposal is needed and evaluated by a panel. This does lead to a higher threshold. In contrast, thanks to their open-door policy, support from the SoDa team is more easily accessible.

Task Leader: Rob van Nieuwpoort (R.vanNieuwpoort@esciencecenter.nl)

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Rob van Nieuwpoort (R.vanNieuwpoort@esciencecenter.nl)

3.4.5 Benchmarking

Benchmarking is about creating a system of reference, in which various models that address the same task can be compared, in order to be able to analyse the strength and weaknesses of various approaches and gain new insights. For computer scientists, benchmarks provide a standardized way to validate predictive models that have proven to be able to detect major breakthroughs, like deep learning. When Geoffrey Hinton submitted his convolutional neural network AlexNet to the ImageNet challenge (a computer vision benchmark) it showed a dramatic increase in performance, which boosted the field of neural networks and artificial intelligence in general.

One of the first examples of benchmarking is the Netflix Prize. Netflix challenged data scientists to make their system for recommending movies to their users, based on what they already watched, 10% better in terms of accuracy. They provided example data and the metrics to measure accuracy. The actual performance of participating methods was determined on data that only Netflix had access to. Although the prize

money of 1 million dollars might have initially incentivised people to work on this problem, in the end, the money was donated to charity, and it was more about the value of the data shared and how much knowledge was gained when working on this problem. The availability of the real-world Netflix data with a clearly defined task (a common goal) boosted the academic field of recommender systems.

In computer science, benchmarks are mostly used to validate predictive models, whereas the focus of social scientists lies mostly on causality and explanation. Whether social systems can be predicted is debatable, but causality, explanation and prediction are three sides of the same coin that can supplement and strengthen each other to gain insight into the full picture of the coin. The aim of this task is to design and set-up a benchmark for social sciences that addresses a real-world problem that social scientists are working on and preferably draws from various data sources. We aim to contact the various planning bureaus (e.g. Nivel, SCP, PBL, RIVM), which are ODISSEI members, to inquire if they could provide a real world problem and data. The work will be initiated in 2021-2022, at a cost of € 23,170 for the year, and run until the end of the roadmap project. The work will be led by Paulina Pankowska in collaboration with the coordination team and SoDa.

Task Leader: Paulina K. Pankowska

Coordination Team Contact: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

Management Board Contact: Rob van Nieuwpoort (R.vanNieuwpoort@esciencecenter.nl)

4 Financial Plan 2021-2022

ODISSEI aligned the reporting schedule of (a) the Task Leaders to the Management Board, (b) the Management Board to the Supervisory Board, and (c) ODISSEI to NWO. For this reason, the financial year now runs from 1 July to 30 June. The table below summarises the financial allocations requested by the task leaders and approved by the management board for the year 2021-2022. This is in line with the budget proposals in the initial roadmap application. For specific description of each task and the use of its budget, please see section 3.

Table 2 – Budget Plan for 2021-2022 (with 2020-21 for reference)

	(in €)	2020-2021	2021-2022
Data Facility		1,190,961	1,317,493
1.1 Microdata		394,000	360,000
1.2 Use Cases		40,000	45,412
1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer		615,223	638,004
1.4 Portal		141,738	274,077
Observatory		829,090	1,014,616
2.1 Data collection		697,909	809,770
2.2 MCAL		60,273	61,538
2.1 HSN		70,909	72,398
2.1 NTR		0	70,909
Laboratory		493,147	739,168
3.1 Distributed Learning		66,216	89,157
3.2 Automatic Linking		70,909	72,398
3.4 LISS		260,000	520,000
3.4 Mass Online Experiments		19,204	57,614
3.5 Citizen Science		76,818	0
Hub		478,854	834,568
4.1 Community management		205,876	354,933
4.2 Education		10,000	40,376
4.3 SoDa		96,645	224,257
4.4 eScience Grants		166,333	191,833
4.5 Benchmarking		0	23,170
Total		2,992,052	3,905,845

5 Key Performance Indicators

ODISSEI maintains a register of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) that were initiated at the beginning of the current Roadmap period. Each year the current status of each KPI is reported upon and new targets are established. The KPI are proposed by the Coordination Team and Management Board and amended and approved by the ODISSEI Supervisory Board to ensure continuity and alignment with regards to the specific and concrete aims of the project.

Table 3 - Key Performance Indicators

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Target</i>	<i>Current</i>
Development		
<i>Participation of economics faculties</i>	<i>All social science and economics faculties to be full ODISSEI members by 2025</i>	<i>All social science faculties are members. Several economics faculties still to sign up.</i>
<i>Participation in European projects</i>	<i>Active participation in at least two European Level projects by 2025</i>	<i>New work programme published in summer 2021</i>
<i>International collaborations</i>	<i>Formal collaboration with similar initiatives in UK, US, FR, and DE</i>	<i>Initial contact has been made with discussion of formalization</i>
Data Access		
<i>Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations submitting a proposal</i>	<i>Receive project proposals from 10% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations</i>	<i>Currently approximately 7% of researchers have submitted</i>
<i>Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations being granted a project</i>	<i>Provide access to 5% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations by 2025</i>	<i>Currently 1% of researchers have received a grant</i>
<i>Number of unique visitors to the ODISSEI Portal</i>	<i>No current target set</i>	<i>None as Portal is still in development</i>
<i>Number of projects spanning multiple Work streams</i>	<i>By 2025, at least five projects should have used infrastructure from multiple Work streams simultaneously</i>	<i>1 project using multiple elements with 3 further projects starting by the end of 2021</i>
Financial		
<i>Project money from further projects</i>	<i>Participation in a successful 2022 Roadmap Application for SSH</i>	<i>Preparations of 2022 Roadmap proposal under way</i>
<i>Total amount committed by member organisations</i>	<i>By 2025, to receive continuation of existing commitments to 2029 as a minimum</i>	<i>Current contributions are perpetual but no commitments until 2029</i>
Training & Education		
<i>Number of attendees at training events and workshops</i>	<i>600 unique attendees at events per year</i>	<i>404 for 2020-2021</i>
<i>Number of faculties cooperating in educational program</i>	<i>All ODISSEI member organisations that are university faculty to be integrated into educational program</i>	<i>Educational Program still under development</i>
<i>Number of researchers supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa)</i>	<i>No current target set</i>	<i>For 2020-2021 this was 4</i>

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Target</i>	<i>Current</i>
Science & Technology		
<i>Number of scientific papers describing the infrastructure</i>	<i>3 per year over 5 years</i>	<i>For 2020-2021 this was 2</i>
<i>Number of peer-reviewed publications derived from ODISSEI research projects</i>	<i>30 per year by 2025</i>	<i>8 in the period 2020-21</i>
<i>Number of citations received for publications derived from ODISSEI research projects</i>	<i>No current target set</i>	<i>23 in the period 2020-21</i>
Impact for Industry		
<i>Number of datasets contributed by industry partners</i>	<i>Five datasets from industry partners contributed by 2025</i>	<i>None</i>
<i>Number of sectors from which industry partners are derived</i>	<i>Partners from more than one sector by 2025</i>	<i>None</i>
Impact for Society		
<i>Number of government agencies participating as member organisations</i>	<i>No current target set</i>	<i>5</i>
<i>Number of website visits</i>	<i>No current target set</i>	<i>9,200 in 2020-21</i>
<i>Press mentions in the Netherlands</i>	<i>No current target set</i>	<i>Monitoring not yet operational</i>
Communication		
<i>Number of social media subscribers</i>	<i>Total of 5,000 by 2025</i>	<i>593</i>
<i>Number of newsletter subscribers</i>	<i>Total of 8,000 by 2025</i>	<i>596</i>
Attracting New Talent		
<i>Number of international researchers recruited by ODISSEI partners</i>	<i>No current target set</i>	<i>Monitoring not yet operational</i>
<i>Number of international projects (such as MSCA) using ODISSEI</i>	<i>No current target set</i>	<i>None</i>

6 Risk Register

The ODISSEI Risk register is designed to support the strategic planning and decision making of the Coordination Team, the management board and the Supervisory Board. The risks identified by each task leader are consolidated into a single risk register. The full risk register appears at the end of this document and has been used to create an overview of the various challenges faced by ODISSEI. Risk assessments are always subjective but consolidating the risk assessments into a singular document can help identify common risks, differences in risk perceptions across the project and interdependent mitigation strategies.

Across the project there were 5 risks which were identified as highly likely to happen and to have a high impact on the implementation of the task. All the risks have been explicitly discussed by the Management Board and are being actively monitored by task leaders and Coordination Team contacts.

Risks related to staffing were also identified across multiple work streams. ODISSEI tasks require complex translational skills and advanced technical, practical and scientific knowledge. Ensuring high quality recruitment, as well as training and development opportunities is a considerable challenge in ODISSEI. With regards to both FAIR and staffing risks, it is not explicitly stated who is responsible for these risks within the current ODISSEI management framework.

There are risks associated with the scalability of the infrastructure and the sustainability beyond 2024. These risks are key strategic concerns of the ODISSEI Management Board. Finally, there were a number of legal and ethical issues identified within ODISSEI. These risks are clearly identified and addressed by clear ownership of the risk at the level of task leader.

Table 4 - High Probability, High Impact Risks

<i>Task</i>	<i>Mitigation</i>
1.1 Unequal usage of the MAD across scientific domains and categories of users	Reconsider the discount distribution model
1.3 A new Supercomputer will arrive at SURF before 2024. The team must adopt to the new Supercomputer environment.	Once it is known what the new supercomputer is (in terms of hardware, software, operating system), the team will plan for transition of OSSC to the new Supercomputer. A transition period will be determined to have the OSSC running on the current supercomputer, while setting up and configuring the service on the new Supercomputer.
2.1 No further funding for data collections	The financing strategy must identify cost reduction measures and a new financing strategy and stimulate the respective survey communities to collaborate on funding applications
4.1 Limited opportunity for in-person meetings, due to the corona crisis	The team will select the best possible software for online events. The team will adapt the programme to make it suitable for an online event.
4.5 No interest from social scientists	Involving social scientists from before start of design through sessions at conferences

Figure 2 - Risks by area

The 72 risks were broadly categorized, and a summary of the results are above. When grouping the risks by area, key patterns emerge. The top three risk areas are easily identifiable within a project such as ODISSEI. As a federated, distributed infrastructure issues of coordination are always of paramount concern and were a key rationale behind developing a strong central hub and coordination team. ODISSEI is also very complex, and the technical risks represent those risk which are associated with scientific, methodological or technical issues which are primarily associated with specific tasks. Finally, it is reassuring that almost all tasks are aware of the need for services to cater for an active research community and this is represented by the risk of low demand. These three risks are broadly addressed in the design of ODISSEI as a project and ownership of these risks lies with the coordination team and respective task leaders.

The next two risks are more specific. Risks associated with data availability and documentation have been grouped under 'FAIR'. FAIR implementation is a known issue within parts of ODISSEI and was identified as a significant risk in the Data Facility and Laboratory tasks. It is likely that the risks associated with FAIR implementation have not been identified or considered sufficiently in the Observatory and Hub tasks and this point will be raised with task leaders in future. A coordinated strategy for FAIR implementation across the project, led by Jacco van Ossenbruggen and Lucas van der Meer will help task leaders identify and address these risks.

Risks related to Staffing were also identified across multiple work streams. ODISSEI tasks require complex translational skills and advanced technical, practical and scientific knowledge. Ensuring high quality recruitment, as well as training and development opportunities is a considerable challenge in ODISSEI. With regards to both FAIR and Staffing Risks, it is not explicitly stated who is responsible for these risks within the current ODISSEI management framework.

There are risks associated with the scalability of the infrastructure and the sustainability beyond 2024. These risks are key strategic concerns of the ODISSEI Management Board. Finally, there were a number of legal and ethical issues identified within ODISSEI. These risks are clearly identified and addressed by clear ownership of the risk at the level of task leader.

Table 5 - Full Risk Register

Task	number	Risk	Probability	Impact	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
Data Facility						
1.1	1	Restrictions in the usage of CBS microdata, e.g., as a follow-up of the external investigation into the security of Microdata Services	1	3	Increase technical and procedural safety warrants so that the research process itself is not affected more than necessary	Legal
1.1	2	Lack of documentation in English limits the usability for non-Dutch researcher	3	2	CBS Data Service Centre next generation is aiming for including metadata description in English, but realization is still uncertain	FAIR
1.1	3	Increased usage to an extent that the MAD percentage to an undesirably low level, that might cause some members to consider leaving ODISSEI	2	2	Reconsider the discount distribution model	High Demand
1.1	4	Unequal usage of the MAD across scientific domains and categories of users	3	3	Reconsider the discount distribution model	Low Demand
1.1	5	Innovations selected as most useful according to the user need inventory are not feasible within time and budget	1	2	Propose smaller scale, stepwise innovations in agreement with the user council	Sustainability
1.1	6	Innovations proposed in the user need inventory are not compatible with the new safety regulations that results from the CBS re-evaluation of the safety of the RA facility	2	2	Adapt the proposals to fit the safety regulations or select different measures from the inventory	Legal
1.3	1	A new Supercomputer will arrive at SURF before 2024. The team must adopt to the new Supercomputer environment.	3	3	Once it is known what the new supercomputer is (in terms of hardware, software, operating system), the team will plan for transition of OSSC to the new Supercomputer. A transition period will be determined to have the OSSC running on the current supercomputer, while setting up and configuring the service on the new Supercomputer.	Technical
1.3	2	Misalignment between SURF and CBS	1	2	The team will have periodic meetings	Coordination
1.3	3	Too difficult user interface	2	2	Working on a graphic interface, education (Roadmap task 4.2)	Technical
1.3	4	Scalability (of support). Currently the team has capacity problems with the support it can provide for new research projects, this is due to the limited level of	2	2	(Internally) hire more staff for user support. Minimise the required user support by offering HPC trainings and user documentation. Minimise the required user support by offering HPC trainings and user	High Demand

Task number	Risk	Probability	Impact	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
	resources available for user support in the project and the unforeseen circumstances it faced with loss of a colleague.			documentation. Raise awareness within the community and users about the existing trainings on usage of HPC systems. Offered by SURF	
1.4 1	Not being able to hire appropriate staff	1	3	Widely setting out vacancies, possibility to outsource the hiring.	Staffing
1.4 2	Misalignment (strategic or technical) between the partners	2	3	Bi-weekly, low-profile steering group and technical meetings	Coordination
1.4 3	Potential metadata providers not willing to or able to (automatically) share metadata, or to invest in altering metadata	2	3	Representatives in the ODISSEI Management Board. Cooperating with the ODISSEI Fieldwork Committee. Offering support to metadata providers.	FAIR
1.4 4	Insufficient need for what we develop	2	3	Three-monthly user tests, presenting early versions at conferences, creating use cases, close collaboration with the social science research community.	Low Demand
1.4 5	Challenge to integrate the different components into one system	2	2	Coordination between partners and commonly designing technical infrastructure	Coordination
1.4 6	Lack of commitment for sustaining infrastructure after period 4	1	3	DANS committed to sustain the built infrastructure for at least five years.	Sustainability
1.4 7	Insufficient knowledge and consensus on explicit semantics of social-science metadata to develop a search interface with sufficient added value for social science researchers	2	3	Make use of existing standardisation efforts in the community, including the CEESDA metadata models and thesauri.	FAIR
Observatory					
2.1 1	High non-response in online data collections	3	2	Knowledge exchange and shared results of online data collection	Technical
2.1 2	Disruptions to fieldwork due to COVID	2	2	Most data collection has now been transferred to online only	Technical
2.1 3	Low cooperation with data scouts	2	1	Data Scouts need to be well embedded within the ODISSEI community and aware of the value added by ODISSEI	Coordination
2.1 4	No further funding for data collections	3	3	The financing strategy must identify cost reduction measures and a new financing strategy and stimulate the respective survey communities to collaborate on funding applications	Sustainability
2.2 1	Not embedded in wider ODISSEI community	1	3	Ensure regular contact between MCAL team and wider ODISSEI Tasks (see 4.7)	Coordination
2.2 2	Shifting investment and user requirements	3	2	The content analysis landscape is very dynamic, and an agile approach is therefore being adopted for its development	Low Demand
2.3 1	Delays in project implementation at CBS	1	3	Contact should be made with the CBS representative on the MB	Coordination

Task number	Risk	Probability	Impact	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
2.3 2	The number of records is insufficient for certain types of analysis	3	1	Initial research applications will be developed that can at least demonstrate the potential for linkage and applications	Technical
2.3 3	Low usage of linked data file	1	2	Extensive events to raise awareness of the linked data and potentially collaborative events with CLARIAH and other SSH RI.	Low Demand
2.4 1	SOP from De Zeeuw et al. does not function on Snellius.	1	3	Consult with SURF partners	Technical
2.4 2	No other cohorts wanting to invest in linkage project	1	2	Through multiple consortia in NL we are well connected to approach PIs	Low Demand
2.4 3	Ethical barriers to linkage	1	3	SURF as TTP is accepted	Legal
2.4 4	Historical data difficult to combine with CBS	2	2	Optimize info in CBS itself	Technical
2.4 5	Not possible to develop MZ-DZ algorithm	2	2	Develop analytical strategy (mixture models); explore linkage to databases of data on newborns	Technical

Laboratory

3.1 1	The data required to undertake the study is not available or unsuitable for large scale analysis.	2	1	The concern largely relates to the quality of proxy outcomes, which may be embedded in free text as opposed to enumerated categories. If necessary, we will develop a separate data cleaning step to manual curate the data for eventual large scale processing.	FAIR
3.1 2	Parental consent will be required to pursue the proposed research questions.	1	3	Preliminary analysis suggests that there should be viable routes that do not require consent. In the event that consent is required, we will reformulate the research questions and use data that are available and does not require consent. We will still be able to demonstrate all other aspects of the proposed research.	Legal
3.1 3	Collaborating organisations are no longer able to participate	1	2	In the event that specific individuals from the NRO, Directorate, and CBS partners are no longer available, we will seek suitable replacements from those organisations. If it is not feasible to continue partnering with any part of those organisations, we will reformulate our plans where possible, and the likely impact is a reduction in the overall ambition (likely affecting deliverable D4).	Coordination
3.1 4	CBS no longer provides a secure computing environment for the distributed learning experiment	1	1	We will seek to partner or purchase access with existing commercial grade secure processing environments. This may cause an increase in the operational costs owing to platform access fees.	Coordination
3.1 5	The technical expertise within the Maastricht team is no longer available.	2	1	None of the personnel have permanent contracts; Chang Sun is a 4th year PhD student that is slated to complete her degree requirements by the end of 2021. Birgit Wouters is also slated to defend her thesis in	Staffing

Task number	Risk	Probability	Impact	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
				2021. If either declines the opportunity to continue in a postdoc fashion, we will either recruit a new researcher or involve one of the other 25 researchers at the Institute of Data Science.	
3.2 1	Limited availability of quality metadata from DANS, LISS and CBS	2	3	limit to available providers and include external providers (e.g. CEESDA), soft power via ODISSEI	FAIR
3.2 2	Change of metadata schema and vocabularies	3	1	We chose for a extensible and flexible data approach in combination with a modular software approach with the use of a mapping template solution	FAIR
3.2 3	Stability of the cloud infrastructure from SURF	1	3	Keeping a good backup and versioning strategy of the source code and data, user of container and virtual machine technology where applicable.	Technical
3.3 1	Interest in ODISSEI LISS Calls is limited	1	3	Invest more efforts in advertising the Calls, and promotion of the possibilities the Calls offers	Low Demand
3.3 2	Interest in ODISSEI LISS Calls is overwhelming, leading to very low award rate	2	2	Make calls more thematically focused; merge funds for two calls; limit the target population to e.g. early career researchers only	High Demand
3.3 3	Attrition LISS panel is non-random making the panel less representative of the Dutch (speaking) population	2	3	Intensify panel care; correct for biases with stratified refreshment samples; increase efforts to minimize attrition; if needed reallocate budget to fund additional refreshment samples	Technical
3.3 4	Response rates decrease in monthly questionnaires and experiments fielded in the LISS panel	2	2	Motivate respondents to participate using response-enhancing measures, e.g. attractiveness of questionnaires and experiments, higher monetary incentives	Technical
3.3 5	Many panel members stop participating due to personal data breaches	1	3	Continuously monitor data security. Act proactively in case of a personal data breach or data leak	Legal
3.3 6	Increasing number of respondents opt-out when asked permission to link LISS data to register data, making linking less attractive for scientific research	2	2	Better explain what linking entails and that no identifying information will be made public	Technical
3.3 7	Delay in dissemination data via the LISS Data Archive due to restricted personnel capacity	1	2	Increase capacity; prioritize disseminations (first disseminate modules core study, then ODISSEI LISS Call projects, followed by other projects)	FAIR
3.3 8	Funding via the Domeinplan-SSH stops	1	3	Intensify efforts to acquire external funding	Sustainability
3.4 1	Example studies are not completed in time	1	3	Frequent contact between task leaders and collaborators. Documentation of the process to at least learn from challenges on the way, and to be able to report intermediate results	Coordination

Task number	Risk	Probability	Impact	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
3.5 1	No access to data	1	3	Change to another citizen science dataset, some of which are already available.	FAIR
3.5 2	Technical case is too complicated to carry out entirely	2	1	In this case, the technical case will just be described, and no servers linking to private data will be set up. Implementation is postponed to the next phase of the project	Technical
3.5 3	Unavailability of staff	1	3	Risk here is low, because staff has already been hired, and has time reserved for this project.	Staffing
Hub					
4.1 1	Researchers are hard to reach and/or too busy	2	3	The team will keep events concise. The team will make information easily accessible online.	Coordination
4.1 2	Limited opportunity for in-person meetings, due to the corona crisis	3	3	The team will select the best possible software for online events. The team will adapt the programme to make it suitable for an online event.	Coordination
4.1 3	Community Managers do not have enough scientific knowledge	2	2	The team will have regular meetings with the entire Coordination Team, to keep up to date. The team will direct researchers to the people who can help them with the scientific or computational challenges (such as ODISSEI's Social Data Science Team (SoDa)).	Staffing
4.1 4	An overload of ODISSEI communication, which lessens the interest of potential users.	1	2	The team will keep track of communication output in a Content Calendar.	Low Demand
4.2 1	Researchers are hard to reach and/or too busy	2	3	The education team will keep ODISSEI events concise. It will strive to match what it offers to researchers' needs.	Low Demand
4.2 2	Limited opportunity for in-person meetings, due to the corona crisis	3	3	The team will select the best possible software for online events. It will adapt the event programme to fit online possibilities.	Coordination
4.2 3	Task team members do not have enough scientific knowledge	2	2	The task team will have regular meetings with the rest of the Coordination Team, to keep up to date. It will work closely with partners who do have specific knowledge on specific topics.	Staffing
4.2 4	Demand for courses is too high	2	2	The task team will scale up events, and when needed it will assist in coordinating 'train the trainer' events in cooperation with ODISSEI partners.	High Demand
4.2 5	Demand for training is too low	2	3	The task team will work with the Community Management task (4.1) to increase ODISSEI's visibility, so information about the events can be spread as wide as possible.	Low Demand
4.3 1	Not obtaining appropriate time investments from researchers	1	3	Selection of researchers based on time commitment (in addition to project criteria), e.g., the researchers (not SoDa) carry main responsibility for substantive papers with SoDa collaboration	Coordination

Task number	Risk	Probability	Impact	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
4.3 2	Not reaching the non-academic researchers (e.g. planbureaus)	3	1	None (not actively seeking out collabs, but open to them); reusability of software products -> possibility of usage outside academia (see ASReview)	Coordination
4.3 3	Not being able to keep the team's knowledge state of the art	3	2	No person on earth has state-of-the-art knowledge. Mitigation is continuing training & education in collaboration with UU Information & Technology Services (ITS) and NLeScC; collaboration with experts in our network (e.g. UU focus area ADS)	Staffing
4.3 4	In the team, not being able to cover the wide range of required skills	1	3	(1) By spending 1 fte on wide expertise of UU ITS team, wide range of skills available; (2) network of experts in UU focus area ADS (3) participating in SIGs of NLeSC.	Staffing
4.3 5	Not finding sufficient projects	2	3	Active acquisition, close collaboration with community management, close collaboration with operational management	Low Demand
4.4 1	Fewer applications than expected	2	2	Allocate the remaining available money to the next call round to award more grants than initially planned.	Low Demand
4.4 2	Not reaching sufficient social scientists	2	3	Collaborating with the ODDISSEI community managers to plan and organize an information day regarding the call for social science researchers. Enhance visibility through newsletters and social media.	Coordination
4.4 3	More applications than expected	2	2	Move funding forward to grant more projects, and acquire more funding for periods 2 & 3. Limit the scope of the calls, for example by using a thematic call, focussing on specific technologies (e.g., geospatial, visual analytics, etc.)	High Demand
4.4 4	Projects that are too complex to fit within the available hours	2	2	Organize information day and consultations hours with NLeSC and SoDa teams to advise on a fitting project plan.	Sustainability
4.4 5	No funding available for calls in 2024 and beyond (needs additional funding)	2	3	Explore options for a joint eScience - ODISSEI call early in the process, after the first call round (i.e., early 2022).	Sustainability
4.5 1	Difficulties in recruitment of challenge participants	2	3	Connect to comp soc sci or ML conference challenge track	Low Demand
4.5 2	No interest from social scientists	3	3	Involving social scientists from before start of design through sessions at conferences	Low Demand

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